

ISic0145

I.Sicily inscription 0145

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. T(itus) Cesti[usRu]
2. fus v[ix](it) [an(nis)]
3. VIII

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini

Translation (en)

Titus Cesti[us Ru]fus; he lived 8 years.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285032

EDR 111025

EDCS 22100085

Bibliography

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Bivona, L. 1994. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese. *Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica.* Palermo / Rome. At 64

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